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Research Article

**PUBLIC AWARENESS TOWARDS GERD AMONG SAUDI
POPULATION IN AL-DAMMAM CITY, SAUDI ARABIA**

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Abstract:

Background: Gastro-esophageal reflux disease [GERD] known as one of the most common gastrointestinal disorders visit clinics and ER. Also, it affects patient's lifestyle negatively. There are many doctors confuse this disease with heart diseases such as angina.

Objective: To assess the level of awareness toward GERD signs, symptoms, risk factors and methods of treatment among Saudi population in Al-Dammam City. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study based on questionnaire that was distributed among the general public in Al-Dammam City, Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire consist of two sections: first was included social-demographic information and the second section was to assess the level of awareness and knowledge about the most common symptoms and risk factors related to GERD. **Results:** In this study, 250 participants were filled the surveys. Male participants were more than females [54% and 46% respectively]. More than third of the participants aged between 20 and 30 years. The most common source to obtain information among participants was relatives [66%]. most of participants know that heart burn, regurgitation and chest pain are the most common symptoms GERD patients have with [84%, 77%, 62%] respectively. most of participants chose smoking and alcohol consume as the most common risk factors for GERD [87.2%] and [86%] respectively. The vast majority of participants [82%] believe that lifestyle modification can treat GERD and [86%] of participants do not believe that surgical treatment is a method to treat GERD. **Conclusion:** participants show good knowledge and they have acceptable awareness towards the symptoms and risk factors of GERD and most of them obtained their knowledge from their relatives thus We recommend providing health information concerning GERD on the Internet and to increase the health campaigns to increase the level of awareness among general population.

Keywords: Gastro-esophageal reflux disease, Risk factors, Knowledge, Awareness.

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastro-esophageal reflux disease [GERD] is one of the most common chronic disorders related to digestive system which it results from lower esophageal sphincter dysfunction which leads to reflux the content of stomach back to esophagus [1]. The prevalence of GERD was reported to be high 20% in Western world [2].

Esophageal reflux diseases may present with various of symptoms such as burning sensation and pain in retrosternal area. Esophageal reflux disease symptoms included heartburn, regurgitation and chest pain. The main point for making the diagnosis is clinical history of esophageal symptoms and exclusion. There are many important details should be obtained by taking proper history to exclude other diseases especially lethal diseases such as malignancy. Questions to exclude malignance including weight loss, gastrointestinal bleeding, smoking and alcohol consumption [3].

Patients seek to medical advice because of heartburn and regurgitation and asking for diagnostic evaluation and treatment. Studies showed that GERD may significantly reduce the quality of life and lead to serious complications, such as gastrointestinal bleeding, Barrett's esophagus and ended with malignancy [4].

There are many risk factors such as lifestyle [alcohol consumption, smoking, NSAIDs using] and dietary factors could be predispose to GRED, however the exact etiology is still unknown [5,6].

Obtaining proper history is important to evaluate and diagnosis esophageal reflux disease. Most of patients with GERD can recognize the symptoms of the disease easily and seek medical help. The aim of

this study was to evaluate the knowledge and the level of awareness toward GERD symptoms, risk factors and methods of treatment among general population in Al-Dammam city, Saudi Arabia.

METHODS:**Study design**

A cross-sectional study based on questionnaire that was distributed on 250 participants randomly in Al-Dammam city. Including criteria was any Saudi citizens, age 20 years old and above.

Research tool

The questionnaire included two sections; first section is demographics information including [age, gender, marital status, history of GERD, and sources of information]. The second part was to assess the level of awareness towards GERD symptoms, risk factors and methods of treatment.

Statistical analysis

Data entering and analysis was carried out using SPSS version 22.

RESULTS:

In this study, 250 participants were filled the surveys. Male participants were more than females [54% and 46% respectively]. The majority of participants are married [87.2%] and only [12.8%] are single. More than third of the participants were aged 20-30 years old and participants who aged between 31-40 years old were [31%]. Regarding the history of GERD among participants, the majority of participants had history of GERD [76.8%]. The most common source to obtain information among participants were relatives [66%], internet [19.6%] and only [14.4%] obtain from books and health campaigns. [Table 1].

Table [1]: Socio-demographic information of the participants [250]:

		N [Total =250]	%
sex	Male	135	54%
	female	115	46%
Marital status	Single	32	12.8%
	Married	218	87.2%
age	20-30	94	37.6%
	31-40	78	31.2%
	41-50	52	20.8%
	More than 50	26	10.4%
History of GERD	No	192	76.8%
	Yes	58	23.2%
Sources of information	relatives	165	66%
	internet	49	19.6%
	Books & Health campaigns	36	14.4%

The second table illustrates the level of awareness towards GERD symptoms, risk factors and methods of treatment among general population, most of participants know that heart burn, regurgitation and chest pain are the most common symptoms in GERD patients with [84% , 77%, 62%] respectively. In addition, about half of the participants know that globus sensation, dysphagia and odynophagia are symptoms of GERD. Regarding risk factors, most of participants chose smoking and alcohol consume as the most common risk factors for GERD [87.2%] and [86%]

respectively. The majority of participants know that obesity is risk factor of developing GERD [79.6%]. Regarding the methods of treatment, [82%] of participants believe that lifestyle modification is effective methods to treat the GERD. About two-third of participants believe that GERD could be treated medically while only [13.6%] believe that this diseases could be treated surgically.

[Table 2].

Table 2: shows the questions regarding the symptoms, risk factors and methods of treatment [N=250]:

Questions	N	%
Symptoms:		
Heartburn	210	84%
Regurgitation	193	77.2%
Chest pain	155	62%
Globus Sensation	133	53.2%
Dysphagia	130	52%
Odynophagia	124	49.6%
Risk factors:		
Smoking	218	87.2%
Alcohol	215	86%
Obesity	199	79.6%
Pregnancy	127	50.8%
Methods of treatment:	True	False
Lifestyle modification	205 [82%]	45[18%]
Medication	158[63.2%]	92[36.8%]
surgery	34[13.6%]	216[86.4%]

DISCUSSION:

GERD is one of the most common disorder that affect digestive system. General population showed good knowledge towards GERD. Having good knowledge about GERD's symptoms, risk factors and methods of treatment is very important have good quality of life and to prevent its complications. There are few studies evaluated patient knowledge and level of awareness toward GERD. **There is one study** conducted to assess the degree of knowledge in Korean patients with GERD showed most identified GERD manifestations were heart burn [84%], regurgitation [77.2%], and chest pain [62%] [7]. another study, which was conducted among medical students, the participant's information about GERD was derived mostly from the books and internet [71% and 17% respectively] or health campaigns [10.4%][8]. The main symptoms of GERD included heartburn, regurgitation, chest pain [3]. In the current study the most identified GERD manifestations were

heart burn [84%], regurgitation [77.2%], and chest pain [62%]. The manifestations that were less identified included globus sensation, dysphagia and odynophagia [53.2%, 52% and 49.6 % respectively]. **Du Jeong *et al.* [7]** also found that the two most typical symptoms of gastro- oesophageal reflux disease are heartburn and regurgitation. Heartburn is characterized by a painful retrosternal burning sensation. [7]. Risk factors of GERD included: alcohol, smoking, , obesity and pregnancy, [9,10]. In the current study, the most recognized risk factors of GERD were smoking [87.2%], alcohol [86%], obesity [76.9%] and pregnancy [55.8%]. These results indicated that the participants had a relatively good knowledge of the risk factors. However, more educational programs would be expected to decrease the rates and severity of GERD, particularly as many of the risk factors are preventable. In the current study sex, material status had no effect on level of awareness.

CONCLUSION:

Some symptoms [globus sensation, dysphagia and odynophagia] and risk factor [pregnancy] for GERD remained unknown to nearly half the participants. Educational programs for GERD should focus on these points.

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